

Non-destructive quantitative analysis of five commercially available Indian cement clinkers using powder XRD

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Abstract : Structurally distinguishable phases of the substances present in four hydraulic (Portland) cement samples and in one white cement sample manufactured in India, were identified from their respective XRD diagrams and subsequently quantitatively analyzed using quantitative phase analysis program based on Rietveld refinement (Bish and Howard, 1988). Phases present in all the hydraulic cement samples are tricalcium silicate (Alite and Haturite, C3S), dicalcium silicate (Larnite, C2S), brownmillerite, both orthorhombic and monoclinic phases (tetracalcium aluminoferrate, C4AF) and tricalcium aluminate (C3A). A small amount of gypsum, periclase, bassenite and other minerals were also found to be present in four Portland clinkers, while a sizeable chunk of calcium silicate hydrate gel (CAHG) was found to be present in three samples. In the white cement, as expected, neither form of brownmillerites were detected. Credibility, merits and demerits of the method used were discussed.

Keywords : Cement, Rietveld analysis, X-ray diffraction.

Introduction

Powder diffraction and structure investigations by means of single crystals both originated in 1913 and immediately their path diverged. Soon powder diffractometry started finding application as a potential analytical tool. With the introduction of JCPDS (Joint Commission on Powder Diffraction Standards) files in 1941 (now named ICDD), powder diffractometry became an accepted tool for identification of crystalline phases present in a mixture. But application of powder diffractometry has been revolutionized after the advent of Rietveld method^{1,2}. Now-a-days, Rietveld analysis is finding manifold applications, right from elucidation of crystal structure from powder data to study of cation distribution in a glass matrix. One of the most astounding application of Rietveld method being quantitative phase analysis (QPA)³. This method requires neither any internal standard nor any calibration. It requires information about the crystal structure of the constituent phases in a mixture. Precisely the crystallographic information files (CIFs) of the constituent materials. Advent of QPA using Rietveld method has encouraged analytical chemists to venture for quantitative analy-

sis of more complex systems, such as Portland cement⁴⁻⁶, archaeological ceramics⁷, antique coins⁸ and so on.

Cement industries of Europe and America use QPA to control on-line production process⁴. The relative error in QPA is about 1 wt% in case of synchrotron X-ray analysis and that for a common laboratory diffractometer is about 2 wt%, for main phases and increases to 5-10% for low content compounds⁴. These errors are acceptable in factory environment and in western countries routine analysis applying this methodology is very popular.

Present work aims to analyze four hydraulic (Portland) cements of grade 43 and one white cement widely available in Indian market, using Bish and Howard³ formalism.

Apart from chemical composition, this study provides insight about a few chemicals, such as gypsum (in sample S1) intentionally added by the manufacturers to lower the setting time of the cement clinkers. Up till this date there is no such QPA study on Indian cement clinkers using Rietveld analysis.

Theoretical consideration :

Quantitative phase analysis of a multi-component system viz. cement clinkers, may be achieved with the TOPAS-

3 (Bruker) software using the Rietveld analysis of diffraction data. TOPAS-3 uses a program based on Bish and Howard (1988) formalism. This method does not require any calibration of data nor any internal standard but the CIF files of the constituent materials and consequently powder diffraction pattern is automatically generated and scale factor of each component is refined until a good fit is achieved. Scale factor of each component contains information about weight fractions of respective components. The method is as following :

The intensity of X-rays diffracted by a randomly oriented indefinitely thick polycrystalline sample in flat-plate geometry utilizing a diffracted monochromator is given by :

$$I_{hkl} = \left\{ \left(\frac{I_0 A \lambda^2}{32 \pi r} \right) \left[\left(\frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \right)^2 \frac{e^4}{m^2} \right] \times \left(\frac{1}{2\mu} \right) \times \left(\frac{1}{V^2} \right) \times \left[IFI^2 \rho \left(\frac{1 + \cos 2\theta^2 \cos \theta_m^2}{\sin \theta^2 \cos \theta} \right) \right] \times e^{-2M} \right\} \quad (1)$$

The subscript *hkl* denotes the dependence of particular terms on Bragg reflection *hkl*. The term $2\theta_m$ refers to the diffraction angle of the diffracted beam monochromator crystal and other symbols bears the customary significance.

Eq. (1) may be written as

$$I_{hkl} = K \left(\frac{1}{2\mu_0} \right) R_{hkl} \quad (2)$$

where

$$K = \left(\frac{\mu_0 A \lambda^2}{32 \pi r} \right) \left[\left(\frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \right)^2 \frac{\theta^4}{m^2} \right] \quad (3)$$

$$R_w = \left(\frac{1}{V^2} \right) \left[IFI^2 \rho \left(\frac{1 + \cos 2\theta^2 \cos \theta_m^2}{\sin \theta^2 \cos \theta} \right) \times e^{-2M} \right] \quad (4)$$

In a mixture the intensity of the *hkl* reflection from α phase is given by phase.

$$I_{\alpha,hkl} = C_\alpha K (1/2\mu_m) R_{\alpha,hkl} \quad (5)$$

where C_α is the volume fraction of the α phase μ_m is the linear absorption coefficient of the mixture.

Eq. (5) may be written as

$$I_{\alpha,hkl} = \frac{w_\alpha}{\rho_{\alpha_\alpha}} K (\rho_m / 2\mu_m) R_{\alpha,hkl} \quad (6)$$

where w_α is the weight fraction of the α .

The scale factor in the Rietveld analysis for the α phase is implicitly defined as

$$S_\alpha = \frac{w_\alpha}{\rho_\alpha} \times k \frac{\rho_m}{2\mu_m} \quad (7)$$

Its value is refined unless a good residual is achieved.

Since the sum of weight fraction is unity,

Say there are two phases, viz. α and β .

$$W_\alpha = W_\alpha / (W_\alpha + W_\beta) \quad (8)$$

Eq. (7) can be solved simultaneously for both α and β phases or more phases.

Eq. (7) when substituted in eq. (8) and common terms get cancelled to give

$$W_s = S_\alpha \rho_\alpha / (S_\alpha \rho_\alpha + S_\beta \rho_\beta) \quad (9)$$

ρ_α and ρ_β are densities of α and β phases and can be evaluated as long as unit cell volume and contents are known.

Experimentally observed XRD peaks were fitted with a pseudo-Voigt profile^{9,10}.

Results and discussion

Table 1 depicts results of QPA of four Portland cement and Table 2 depicts results of QPA of a white cement sample. While analyzing, preferred orientation along

Table 1. Results of quantitative phase analysis of four Portland cement clinkers namely S1, S2, S3, S4

Sample name	S1 (wt%)	S2 (wt%)	S3 (wt%)	S4 (wt%)
Alite (C ₃ S)	47.28	25.08	49.71	32.37
Larnite (C ₂ S)	21.09	24.55	15.18	23.08
Brownmillerite-I	17.04	6.11	3.10	7.74
Brownmillerite-II		1.54	4.92	
Tricalcium aluminate (C ₃ A)	5.56	2.01	4.02	7.02
Gypsum	3.45	2.27		1.31
Periclase		1.45		
CAHG			23.57	28.03
Bassanite				
Rankinite				
Quartz	5.57	0.76		0.39
Calcium hexaluminate		4.37		
Hturityte		31.87		
Gunerite				
Portlandite				0.05
<i>R_{wp}</i>	14.69	11.18	7.086	7.55

Fig. 1. Results of Rietveld analysis based quantitative phase analysis of (a) sample S1, (b) Sample S2, (c) sample S3, (d) sample S4 and (e) sample W1.

Table 2. Results of quantitative phase analysis of white cement under study

Sample name	W1 (wt%)
Alite (C ₃ S)	36.19
CAHG	41.44
Larnite (C ₂ S)	8.01
Tricalcium aluminate (C ₃ A)	2.96
Dolomite	6.30
Gypsum	0.41
Bassenite	4.21
Grunerite	0.48
R _{wp}	14.427

10-1 direction was taken into account in case of alite (C₃S) and haturite (C₃S). Similarly preferred orientation along 101 plane was taken into account in case of gypsum. Fig. 1 shows details of QPA based on Rietveld analysis. This method is better than XRF analysis of cement, since XRF of cement normally requires calibration graphs (one for each analyte), which are obtained using appropriate mixtures of certified standards, pure oxides or mixture of both^{11,12}. Other methods, such as, spectrophotometric and conventional chemical analysis are still more cumbersome and time consuming.

Cements we studied are widely sold in Indian market and comply with the standard specified by Bureau of Indian Standard (BIS). Appendix I shows that specifications^{13,14} proposed by BIS comply well with our results when our results were represented in terms of CaO, SiO₂, Al₂O₃, Fe₂O₃ content. In this context we would like to add that BIS specifications are based on results of conventional chemical analysis. C3S content prescribed by BIS is 45% by mass for high quality Portland cements to be used in railway constructions. Our sample S1 contains 47.28% of alite which is a form of C3S. S2 contains 25.08% alite and 31.87% haturite, which is another form of C3S. S3 contains 49.71% of alite but the fourth sample i.e. S4 contain only 32.37% of alite but it complies well with other standards prescribed by BIS for 43 grade ordinary Portland cements. Of course S4 cannot be used in railway sleeper constructions according to our analysis. Our analysis show that tricalcium aluminate (C3A) content in all the cements we studied did not exceed 10% (by mass), which is prescribed by BIS^{13,14}.

In Appendix-I credibility of our results were discussed.

Only short-coming of this method is that CIF file for

a given phase should be available or in other words its structural information should be available in one of the open access websites.

Experimental

X-Ray powder diffraction diagrams of four Portland cement clinkers renamed as S1, S2, S3 and S4 and one white cement renamed as W1 (all are procured from the market) were recorded in a Bruker AXS XRD powder diffractometer (Model no : D8 Advance) fitted with a lynxeye super speed detector in continuous mode and in the range of $2\theta = 5^\circ$ to $2\theta = 110^\circ$ degree with a step-width of 0.02° degree and scan-speed of 2 s. Radiation used was Cu_{Kα1}. Ni filter was used to do away with Cu_{Kβ} radiation. Recordings were done as soon the samples were procured from the market to avoid any possible absorption of moisture on storage.

CIF files were accessed either from the American Mineralogist Crystal Structure Data Base (AMCSDB) or from Crystallographic Open Data Base (COD). Phases present in each cement clinkers were identified using International Crystallographic diffraction data (ICDD). In-built QPA program present in TOPAS-3 supplied by Bruker was made use of to achieve quantitative results.

Appendix-I

According to Taylor¹⁵ composition of alite/haturite, larnite, tricalcium aluminate and brownmillerite/calcium aluminoferrite of Portland cement variety is as following :

Alite (%)	Larnite (%)	Tricalcium aluminate (%)	Brownmillerite (%)
(3CaO.SiO ₂)	(2CaO.SiO ₂)	(3CaO.Al ₂ O ₃)	(2CaO.A ₂ O ₃ .Fe ₂ O ₃)
CaO – 71.6	CaO – 65.02	CaO – 62.24	CaO – 40.2
SiO ₂ – 25.2	SiO ₂ – 34.8	SiO ₂ – 0.8	SiO ₂ – 6.10
Al ₂ O ₃ – 1.00	Al ₂ O ₃ – 0.02	Al ₂ O ₃ – 37.01	Al ₂ O ₃ – 17.0
Fe ₂ O ₃ – 0.7	Fe ₂ O ₃ – 0.01	Fe ₂ O ₃ – 0.01	Fe ₂ O ₃ – 27.7
Calcium hexaaluminate (%)			
(CaO.6Al ₂ O ₃)			
CaO – 8.09			
Al ₂ O ₃ – 91			

Calcium silicate hydrate gel :

There is no data in Taylor's book¹³. However, CAHG may be represented as 3CaO.2SiO₂.4H₂O and accordingly percentage of CaO and SiO₂ were calculated as : CaO – 42.87%.

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From above Table and Table 1, we calculated CaO, SiO₂, Al₂O₃ and Fe₂O₃ content in our cement samples to compare our results with BIS specification¹³.

$$Q = \frac{\text{CaO} - 0.7\text{SO}_2}{2.8\text{SiO}_2 + 1.2\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 + 0.65\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3} \text{ taken from BIS}$$

specification for Portland cement grade 43¹³ (A)

Our result (Portland cement) :

Sample	Q value defined by eq. (A)	Al ₂ O ₃ (%)/ Fe ₂ O ₃ (%)	Chlorine content	C3S (%)	C3A (%)
S1	0.86	0.76	Nil	47.28	5.56
S2	1.02	0.77	Nil	56.00	2.01
S3	1.01	0.69	Nil	49.71	4.02
S4	0.65	0.64	Nil	32.37	7.02

BIS specification

0.66–1.02 min–0.66 <5% >45^a Min 10

^aFor the construction of Railway sleepers.

Similarly from Table 2 and above table, we calculated CaO, SiO₂, Al₂O₃ and Fe₂O₃ content in our white cement and compared the results with BIS specifications¹⁴.

Our result (White cement) :

Sample No.	Q value defined by eq. (A)	Iron oxide (%)	Magnesia (%)	Total sulfur (%)
W1	0.89	Nil	3.00	Negligible

BIS specification for white cement¹⁴

0.66–1.02 > 1.00% > 6.00 2.75–3.00%

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